

Energetic Stability of Saturated Granular Packings under Buoyancy: A Landau-Type Formulation of Static Enthalpy Equilibrium

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Abstract

Saturated granular packings can sustain mechanical loads through a network of grain contacts that forms a load-bearing granular skeleton. However, loose packings may abruptly lose their structural integrity and undergo rapid rearrangement, as observed in phenomena such as spontaneous liquefaction.

In this work we develop an energetic stability framework for saturated granular systems based on the concept of Static Enthalpy Equilibrium (SEE). The stability of a saturated granular packing is formulated in terms of an effective energy landscape in which the porosity n acts as a macroscopic order parameter.

The effective energy results from the competition between structural resistance of the grain contact network and buoyancy-reduced gravitational energy. The resulting effective energy landscape can be written as

$$G_{\text{eff}}(n) = G_{\text{str}}(n) + \frac{C}{1 - n},$$

where the constant C scales with the buoyancy-controlled gravitational energy $(\rho_s - \rho_f) \cdot g$.

Within this formulation a load-bearing granular skeleton corresponds to a metastable minimum of the effective energy landscape. Instability occurs when the curvature of the potential vanishes,

$$\frac{d^2 G_{\text{eff}}}{dn^2} = 0,$$

corresponding to a spinodal instability of the system.

This perspective provides an effective energetic description of stability in athermal granular systems and establishes a connection between geotechnical observations of liquefaction and concepts of metastability and jamming in granular physics.

List of symbols and abbreviations

Symbol	Meaning	Units
G	Gibbs free energy	J
G_{eff}	Effective free energy of the granular packing	J
G_{str}	Structural energy associated with the grain contact network	J
G_{grav}	Gravitational contribution to the effective free energy	J
U	Internal energy	J
p	Pressure	Pa
V	Total volume of the granular system	m^3
V_f	Pore volume (fluid volume)	m^3
V_s	Solid grain volume	m^3
A	Cross-sectional area of the granular column	m^2
H	Height of the granular packing	m
n	Porosity $n = V_f/V$	—
ϕ	Solid volume fraction $\phi = 1 - n$	—
n_0	Porosity of an equilibrium configuration	—
n^*	Critical porosity at which stability is lost	—
ρ_s	Density of the grains	kgm^{-3}
ρ_f	Density of the pore fluid	kgm^{-3}
g	Gravitational acceleration	ms^{-2}
C	Constant scaling the gravitational energy term	J
σ	Total stress	Pa
u	Pore fluid pressure	Pa
σ'	Effective stress	Pa
M	Mobility coefficient in relaxational dynamics	s^{-1}
κ	Curvature of the effective energy landscape $d^2 G_{\text{eff}}/dn^2$	J
τ	Relaxation time	s
δn	Small perturbation of porosity	—

Keywords: *granular materials; saturated granular packings; buoyancy; energy landscape; jamming; metastability; liquefaction.*

1. Introduction

Granular materials exhibit a wide range of mechanical behaviours that differ fundamentally from those of conventional solids or fluids. Depending on their packing structure and external forcing, granular assemblies may behave as rigid load-bearing structures, slowly relaxing particulate systems, or rapidly rearranging flows. Understanding the conditions under which a granular packing can exist as a stable load-bearing structure therefore represents a central problem in the physics of disordered particulate matter.

In recent decades, concepts such as jamming and rigidity transitions have provided important insights into the emergence of mechanical stability in granular systems (Liu & Nagel, 1998; O’Hern et al., 2003; van Hecke, 2010). Within this framework, a jammed state corresponds to a configuration in which the grain contact network forms a mechanically stable structure capable of transmitting stresses. Loss of rigidity occurs when the contact network becomes marginally stable and the system transitions into a dynamically rearranging state.

Saturated granular systems introduce an additional physical ingredient into this picture. When grains are immersed in a fluid, gravity is reduced by buoyancy according to Archimedes’ principle. The stabilizing normal forces acting at grain contacts are therefore controlled by the buoyancy-reduced grain weight

$$(\rho_s - \rho_f) \cdot g,$$

where ρ_s denotes the grain density and ρ_f the density of the surrounding fluid. This quantity represents the fundamental gravitational energy scale governing the stability of saturated granular packings.

Classical soil mechanics describes the behaviour of such systems primarily through stresses transmitted within the grain skeleton. Following Terzaghi’s effective stress principle,

$$\sigma' = \sigma - u,$$

the mechanical state of a saturated soil is expressed through stresses acting at grain contacts. This formulation has proven extremely successful for describing deformation, strength, and consolidation in soils. However, the effective stress concept implicitly assumes that a load-bearing granular skeleton already exists and focuses on how stresses are transmitted within this structure.

A different question arises when considering loose saturated granular packings that may abruptly lose their structural integrity. In such situations, the fundamental issue is not how stresses are transmitted within a granular skeleton, but whether such a skeleton can exist at all under given physical conditions. Addressing this question requires a stability perspective that focuses on the existence of the grain network itself rather than on the stresses within it.

The concept of Static Enthalpy Equilibrium (SEE) was introduced to address this stability problem. In the SEE framework, the existence of a stable granular skeleton is interpreted as the result of a balance between the structural resistance of the grain contact network and buoyancy-controlled gravitational forcing acting on the packing. From this viewpoint, saturated granular packings may occupy metastable structural states whose stability depends on the overall energetic configuration of the system.

The central question addressed in this work is therefore the following:

Can the stability of a saturated granular packing be formulated as a general energetic condition governing the existence of a load-bearing grain skeleton?

We show that the SEE framework can be expressed in terms of an effective energy landscape in which the porosity of the packing acts as a macroscopic order parameter describing the structural state of the system. Within this formulation, a stable granular skeleton corresponds to a metastable minimum of the energy landscape, while instability occurs when the curvature of this landscape vanishes, corresponding to a spinodal condition.

This perspective establishes a direct connection between geotechnical observations of instability and concepts widely used in granular physics, such as metastability, energy landscapes, and the loss of rigidity in disordered particulate systems. In this sense, the SEE framework provides an effective energetic description of the stability of saturated granular systems and offers a bridge between classical soil mechanics and modern approaches in granular physics.

2 – Thermodynamic Perspective

The stability of many physical systems can be understood in terms of effective energy landscapes. Systems with a large number of microscopic degrees of freedom can often be described by coarse-grained potentials that depend on a reduced set of macroscopic variables. Within such a description, stable configurations correspond to minima of an effective energy, while instability is associated with the loss of local convexity of the potential.

Granular materials represent a class of essentially athermal systems in which thermal fluctuations play no significant role. Their mechanical behaviour is governed by contact forces, geometric constraints, and gravitational interactions. Despite the absence of thermal fluctuations, the concept of an energy landscape remains applicable as a coarse-grained description of the structural state of the system.

In this spirit, the stability of a granular packing can be formulated in terms of an effective energy function

$$G_{\text{eff}}(n), \quad (1)$$

which depends on a macroscopic structural variable. In the present work, the porosity n is introduced as this variable. It characterizes the geometric configuration of the packing and thus serves as a natural scalar order parameter describing the structure of the granular skeleton.

The function $G_{\text{eff}}(n)$ should be understood as a coarse-grained energetic description of the system rather than a thermodynamic potential derived from equilibrium statistical mechanics. It captures the competition between stabilizing and destabilizing mechanisms acting on the granular structure and provides a compact description of its possible equilibrium states.

Stationary configurations of the system are defined by the condition

$$\frac{dG_{\text{eff}}}{dn} = 0, \quad (2)$$

which expresses the balance of the effective forces acting on the structural state variable. Mechanical stability requires that the effective energy landscape is locally convex,

$$\frac{d^2 G_{\text{eff}}}{dn^2} > 0, \quad (3)$$

so that small perturbations increase the effective energy and are therefore suppressed.

A loss of stability occurs when the curvature of the effective energy landscape vanishes,

$$\frac{d^2 G_{\text{eff}}}{dn^2} = 0. \quad (4)$$

This condition corresponds to a spinodal instability of the system, marking the boundary beyond which a metastable configuration can no longer exist. At this point the metastable minimum of the energy landscape disappears, and the system undergoes a spontaneous structural rearrangement.

This formulation is directly analogous to Landau-type descriptions of stability in other physical systems, in which a scalar order parameter evolves within an effective potential. In the present case, the porosity plays the role of the order parameter, and the effective energy landscape determines the existence of a mechanically stable granular phase.

In saturated granular systems, gravity is modified by buoyancy according to Archimedes' principle. The effective body force acting on a grain immersed in a fluid is determined by the submerged density contrast

$$(\rho_s - \rho_f) \cdot g,$$

which sets the fundamental gravitational energy scale of the system. This quantity controls the magnitude of the normal forces acting at grain contacts and therefore plays a central role in stabilizing the granular network.

From this perspective, the configuration of a saturated granular packing can be interpreted as the result of a competition between structural resistance of the grain contact network and buoyancy-controlled gravitational forcing. This competition gives rise to an effective energy landscape governing the stability of the system, which will be formulated explicitly in the following sections.

Section 3 – Porosity as the Structural Order Parameter

To formulate the stability of a granular packing in energetic terms, it is necessary to identify an appropriate macroscopic variable that characterizes the structural configuration of the system. Granular assemblies possess a large number of microscopic degrees of freedom, including grain positions, contact orientations, and local stress distributions. For macroscopic stability considerations, however, these details can be coarse-grained into a reduced set of variables describing the overall structure of the packing.

Among these quantities, the most fundamental characteristic of a granular packing is its porosity

$$n = \frac{V_p}{V}, \quad (5)$$

where V_p denotes the pore volume and V the total volume of the system. The complementary quantity

$$\phi = 1 - n \quad (6)$$

represents the solid volume fraction of the packing.

Because the mass of the grains remains constant during structural rearrangements, variations in porosity correspond directly to changes in the spatial configuration of the grain assembly. In this sense, the porosity provides a natural macroscopic measure of the structural state of the packing. Changes in n reflect collective rearrangements of grains that modify both the geometry and the connectivity of the contact network, which in turn determines the ability of the system to transmit forces.

Within the present framework, the porosity is therefore interpreted as a scalar order parameter describing the structural state of the granular skeleton. This interpretation is consistent with the Landau-type formulation introduced in the previous section, in which the stability of the system is governed by an effective energy landscape depending on a macroscopic variable.

The use of a single scalar variable represents a coarse-grained approximation of the underlying granular microstructure. In reality, additional quantities such as coordination number, fabric anisotropy, or force chain structure may influence the mechanical response of the packing. However, during large-scale structural rearrangements—such as those associated with collapse

or liquefaction—grain contacts are continuously broken and reformed, and directional fabric tends to be rapidly destroyed. Under such conditions, the porosity remains the dominant macroscopic variable controlling the existence of a load-bearing network.

In the context of the effective energy formulation, the porosity thus plays the role of an order parameter that determines whether the system can exist in a mechanically stable phase. Stable configurations correspond to values of n for which the effective energy landscape exhibits a metastable minimum, while unstable configurations correspond to regions in which this minimum disappears and the granular skeleton loses its structural integrity.

This interpretation provides a direct link between the geometric description of the packing and the energetic stability framework. The next section develops the explicit form of the effective energy landscape and identifies the contributions that control the stability of saturated granular packings.

Section 4 – Effective Energy Formulation

The energetic description introduced above requires an explicit representation of the contributions governing the structural state of a saturated granular packing. Within the Landau-type framework, the effective energy of the system arises from the competition between two physically distinct mechanisms: the structural resistance of the grain contact network and the gravitational energy of the grain assembly under buoyant conditions.

The structural contribution reflects the mechanical stability provided by grain contacts, frictional constraints, and geometric packing effects. Rearranging the grains requires changes in the contact network and therefore mechanical work. On a macroscopic level, this resistance can be represented by a structural energy term that depends on the packing configuration,

$$G_{\text{str}}(n).$$

The detailed functional form of $G_{\text{str}}(n)$ depends on the microscopic properties of the granular network, including contact geometry and frictional interactions. For the stability analysis developed here, it is sufficient to assume that this function is smooth and that it increases when the system is displaced from mechanically stable configurations.

The second contribution arises from gravity. In a saturated granular system, the effective body force acting on each grain is reduced by buoyancy according to Archimedes' principle. The relevant force scale is therefore determined by the submerged density contrast

$$(\rho_s - \rho_f) \cdot g,$$

which controls the magnitude of the normal forces acting at grain contacts and thus influences the stability of the granular skeleton.

To determine how this gravitational contribution depends on the structural state of the packing, consider a granular column with cross-sectional area A containing a constant mass of grains. The solid grain volume is given by

$$V_s = (1 - n) \cdot V, \tag{7}$$

where V denotes the total volume of the system. For a column geometry,

$$V = A \cdot H, \tag{8}$$

with H representing the height of the granular packing.

Because the mass of the grains remains constant during structural rearrangements, the solid volume V_s is fixed. Combining these relations yields

$$H = \frac{V_s}{A \cdot (1 - n)}. \tag{9}$$

The geometric origin of this relation is illustrated in Figure 1, which shows how an increase in porosity leads to an upward shift of mass and thus to increase in gravitational energy. For a granular column with constant solid volume, an increase in porosity leads to an increase in column height and thus to an upward shift of the centre of mass of the grain assembly.

Figure 1 Schematic representation of a saturated granular column.

Geometric and energetic origin of the gravitational contribution in the SEE framework. A decrease in packing density (increase in porosity n) leads to an increase in column height and an upward shift of the centre of mass. This results in an increase in gravitational potential energy, providing the physical basis for $G_{\text{grav}}(n) \propto \frac{1}{1-n}$.

As a consequence, the gravitational potential energy of the grains increases with increasing porosity. Since the potential energy is proportional to the height of the centre of mass, the gravitational contribution to the effective energy can be approximated as

$$G_{\text{grav}}(n) \propto (\rho_s - \rho_f) \cdot g \cdot \frac{1}{1-n}$$

This relation expresses the fact that loosening the packing raises the centre of mass of the grain assembly and therefore increases its gravitational potential energy. The gravitational contribution can therefore be written in the form

$$G_{\text{grav}}(n) = \frac{C}{1-n}, \quad (10)$$

where the constant C is proportional to the buoyancy-reduced gravitational energy scale,

$$C \propto (\rho_s - \rho_f) \cdot g.$$

Combining the structural and gravitational contributions yields the effective energy landscape governing the stability of the saturated granular packing,

$$G_{\text{eff}}(n) = G_{\text{str}}(n) + \frac{C}{1-n}. \quad (11)$$

This expression defines the effective potential of the system, in which the porosity acts as an order parameter. The stability of the granular skeleton is determined by the shape of this potential, in particular by the existence and curvature of its local minima.

The structure of the effective energy landscape defined by Eq. (11) is illustrated in Figure 2 highlighting the emergence of a metastable minimum and its disappearance at its spinodal boundary. The competition between structural resistance and buoyancy-controlled gravity leads to the emergence of a metastable minimum corresponding to a load-bearing granular skeleton. As the gravitational contribution increases, the shape of the energy landscape changes, the curvature decreases, and the metastable minimum eventually disappears, marking the stability boundary of the system.

This formulation shows that the stability of a saturated granular packing can be understood as a balance between a stabilizing structural term and a destabilizing gravitational contribution. In the Landau-type interpretation, this corresponds to a competition between terms that favour the existence of a stable phase and terms that drive the system toward instability.

Figure 2 Effective free-energy landscape $G_{\text{eff}}(n)$ of a saturated granular packing within the SEE framework.

For a stable configuration a metastable minimum exists, corresponding to a load bearing granular skeleton.

As the gravitational contribution increases, the shape of the energy landscape changes, the curvature decreases, and the metastable minimum disappears at the spinodal point $\kappa(n^*) = 0$, marking the loss of structural energy.

Section 5 – Stability of the Granular Skeleton

The effective energy formulation derived in the previous section provides a natural framework for analysing the stability of saturated granular packings. Within this description, the structural configuration of the system is characterized by the porosity n , which acts as an order parameter. The existence of a load-bearing granular skeleton corresponds to a metastable minimum of the effective energy landscape

$$G_{\text{eff}}(n) = G_{\text{str}}(n) + \frac{C}{1-n}.$$

Equilibrium configurations of the system are defined by the condition that the first derivative of the effective energy with respect to the order parameter vanishes,

$$\frac{dG_{\text{eff}}}{dn} = 0. \quad (12)$$

This condition expresses the balance between the stabilizing structural resistance of the grain contact network and the destabilizing effect of buoyancy-controlled gravity.

The stability of such a configuration is determined by the curvature of the effective energy landscape. A stable or metastable granular skeleton requires that the second derivative of the effective energy is positive,

$$\frac{d^2G_{\text{eff}}}{dn^2} > 0. \quad (13)$$

In this regime, small perturbations of the porosity increase the effective energy and are therefore suppressed by restoring forces within the grain contact network. The system remains trapped in a metastable configuration corresponding to a load-bearing granular skeleton.

Within the Landau-type interpretation, this condition corresponds to the existence of a locally convex minimum of the effective potential. The granular packing can thus be regarded as occupying a metastable phase characterized by a mechanically stable contact network.

As the porosity increases, the relative influence of the structural term $G_{\text{str}}(n)$ decreases compared to the gravitational contribution. As a consequence, the curvature of the effective energy landscape progressively decreases. When the curvature vanishes,

$$\frac{d^2G_{\text{eff}}}{dn^2} = 0, \quad (14)$$

the metastable minimum disappears.

This condition corresponds to a spinodal instability of the effective energy landscape. At this point, the system reaches the boundary beyond which a metastable granular skeleton can no

longer exist. Unlike classical failure criteria based on stress limits, this instability arises from the loss of structural stability of the entire contact network.

Beyond the spinodal point, any small perturbation leads to a decrease of the effective energy. The system can no longer maintain its previous configuration and undergoes spontaneous structural rearrangement. The granular packing transitions from a load-bearing state to a dynamically evolving configuration in which the contact network is continuously reorganized.

In physical terms, this instability corresponds to a buoyancy-controlled loss of rigidity of the granular skeleton. The stabilizing normal forces at grain contacts become insufficient to sustain a coherent load-bearing structure, and the system enters a state of rapid rearrangement. This transition can be interpreted as a loss of jamming in the granular packing.

The Landau-type formulation thus provides a clear interpretation of the stability of saturated granular systems: the existence of a mechanically stable granular skeleton is equivalent to the existence of a metastable minimum of the effective energy landscape, while the collapse of the structure corresponds to a spinodal loss of this metastable state.

Section 6 – Dynamical Evolution and Critical Slowing Down

The stability analysis developed in the previous section describes the conditions under which a saturated granular packing can exist as a metastable load-bearing structure. To understand how the system approaches this instability, it is necessary to consider the dynamical evolution of the structural order parameter n .

Within the present framework, structural rearrangements of the granular packing tend to reduce the effective energy of the system. This behaviour can be described by a relaxational evolution equation of the form

$$\dot{n} = -M \cdot \frac{dG_{\text{eff}}}{dn}, \quad (15)$$

where M is a positive mobility coefficient characterizing the rate at which the granular structure can reorganize. This equation represents an overdamped dynamics in which the order parameter evolves toward configurations of lower effective energy.

This type of evolution is directly analogous to the relaxational dynamics of an order parameter in Landau-type theories of phase transitions. In this sense, the porosity evolves as a non-conserved order parameter governed by the gradient of the effective potential.

To analyse the behaviour near a stable configuration n^* , the effective energy can be expanded in a Taylor series around this point. Because equilibrium requires

$$\left. \frac{dG_{\text{eff}}}{dn} \right|_{n^*} = 0,$$

the leading contribution is quadratic, and the effective energy can be approximated locally as

$$G_{\text{eff}}(n) \approx G^* + \frac{\kappa}{2} (n - n^*)^2, \quad (16)$$

where

$$\kappa = \left. \frac{d^2 G_{\text{eff}}}{dn^2} \right|_{n^*} \quad (17)$$

denotes the curvature of the energy landscape at the stationary configuration. Physically, κ represents the restoring stiffness of the granular skeleton with respect to small structural perturbations.

Substituting this quadratic approximation into the evolution equation yields

$$\dot{n} \approx -M \cdot \kappa \cdot (n - n^*).$$

Introducing the deviation

$$\delta n = n - n^*,$$

the linearized dynamics becomes

$$\dot{\delta n} = -M \cdot \kappa \cdot \delta n.$$

The solution of this equation corresponds to exponential relaxation toward the metastable state,

$$\delta n(t) = \delta n(0) \cdot e^{-t/\tau},$$

with a characteristic relaxation time

$$\tau = \frac{1}{M \cdot \kappa}. \quad (18)$$

This result shows that the relaxation rate of the system is directly controlled by the curvature of the effective energy landscape.

As long as $\kappa > 0$, perturbations decay and the granular skeleton remains mechanically stable. However, as the spinodal boundary is approached, the curvature decreases. In the limit

$$\kappa \rightarrow 0,$$

the relaxation time diverges,

$$\tau \rightarrow \infty.$$

This divergence represents the phenomenon of critical slowing down and provides a dynamic signature of the approaching spinodal instability.

The dependence of the relaxation time on the curvature of the energy landscape is illustrated in figure 3, showing the divergence of τ as $\kappa \rightarrow 0$.

Figure 3 Critical slowing down near the stability boundary of the granular skeleton.

The relaxation time of structural perturbations scales as $\tau = \frac{1}{M\kappa}$. As the curvature of the effective energy landscape approaches zero, the relaxation time diverges, indicating the progressive loss of restoring stiffness of the granular network.

In this regime, the restoring stiffness of the granular network vanishes, and even small perturbations can lead to large structural changes. Once the curvature becomes negative, the metastable minimum disappears entirely, and the system can no longer sustain a load-bearing configuration. The granular packing then undergoes rapid structural rearrangement toward a new configuration of lower effective energy.

In spatially extended systems, the redistribution of pore fluid and grain rearrangements may couple neighbouring regions of the packing. As a consequence, local instabilities can propagate through the system, leading to a collective collapse of extended regions.

Within the Landau-type interpretation, the dynamics of the granular system thus corresponds to a relaxational evolution of a non-conserved order parameter in an effective energy landscape, with the divergence of the relaxation time marking the approach to a spinodal instability.

Section 7 – Critical Porosity and Isostatic Stability

The stability condition derived in the previous sections implies the existence of a critical porosity n^* at which the curvature of the effective energy landscape vanishes,

$$\frac{d^2 G_{\text{eff}}}{dn^2} = 0.$$

At this point, the metastable minimum of the effective potential disappears, and the granular skeleton can no longer exist as a load-bearing structure. Within the Landau-type interpretation, this condition defines the location of the spinodal boundary in the effective energy landscape.

The exact value of n^* depends on the detailed form of the structural energy $G_{\text{str}}(n)$, which reflects the microscopic properties of the granular network. However, useful physical insight into the location of this instability can be obtained from geometric considerations of granular packings.

The structural stability of a granular network is closely related to its solid volume fraction

$$\phi = 1 - n.$$

Random packings of grains approach marginal mechanical stability when the number of contacts between grains becomes just sufficient to maintain force balance. This condition is commonly referred to as isostatic stability of the granular contact network. In three-dimensional systems, this regime typically occurs for solid fractions in the range

$$\phi \approx 0.58 - 0.64.$$

Within this range, the contact network becomes increasingly fragile, and small perturbations can produce large structural rearrangements.

In saturated granular systems, the stabilizing normal forces at grain contacts are reduced by buoyancy. The relevant force scale is determined by the submerged density contrast

$$(\rho_s - \rho_f) \cdot g.$$

Because buoyancy reduces the effective grain weight, the contact forces in saturated packings are smaller than in dry systems. As a consequence, the granular network reaches marginal stability at slightly lower solid fractions than in dry packings.

These considerations suggest that the stability boundary of saturated granular packings occurs near a solid fraction

$$\phi^* \approx 0.60,$$

corresponding to a porosity

$$n^* = 1 - \phi^* \approx 0.40.$$

This value should be interpreted as an order-of-magnitude estimate rather than a universal constant. It lies within the range commonly associated with loosely packed, liquefaction-prone granular materials,

$$n \approx 0.38 - 0.42.$$

Within the SEE framework, this range can be interpreted as the approximate location of the spinodal boundary in the effective energy landscape. Variations in grain density, grain shape, frictional properties, and fluid density will modify the balance between structural resistance and buoyancy-controlled gravity and may therefore shift the precise position of the instability.

From this perspective, the SEE instability can be interpreted as a buoyancy-controlled loss of a metastable granular phase, occurring when the contact network approaches the limit of isostatic stability. The critical porosity n^* thus marks the transition from a mechanically stable to an unstable structural regime in the granular system.

Section 8 – Relation to Classical Soil Mechanics

Classical soil mechanics describes the behaviour of saturated granular materials primarily through the stresses transmitted within the grain skeleton. Following Terzaghi's effective stress principle, the mechanical state of a saturated soil is expressed as

$$\sigma' = \sigma - u,$$

where σ denotes the total stress and u the pore-fluid pressure. This relation expresses the fact that pore pressure reduces the normal stresses acting at grain contacts and therefore controls the mechanical strength of the granular skeleton.

Within this framework, the existence of a load-bearing granular structure is generally assumed. The theory focuses on how stresses are transmitted through the grain network and how this network responds to external loading. As long as the grain skeleton remains mechanically stable, the effective stress formulation provides a powerful and widely used description of deformation, strength, and consolidation in soils.

The SEE framework approaches the problem from a fundamentally different, but complementary perspective. Instead of starting from the mechanical response of an already existing granular skeleton, SEE addresses the more fundamental question of whether such a skeleton can exist under given physical conditions.

Figure 4 Conceptual relation between the SEE framework and classical soil mechanics.

While effective stress describes the transmission of forces within an already existing granular skeleton, the SEE framework addresses the more fundamental question of whether such a skeleton can exist under given physical conditions.

In the Landau-type interpretation developed in this work, the granular packing can be viewed as occupying a metastable phase characterized by a mechanically stable contact network. The stability of this phase is governed by the effective energy landscape $G_{\text{eff}}(n)$, in which the porosity acts as an order parameter. The existence of a load-bearing granular skeleton corresponds to the presence of a metastable minimum of this potential.

The conceptual difference between classical effective stress theory and the SEE framework is illustrated in Figure 4, emphasizing that SEE describes the existence and stability of the granular skeleton, whereas effective stress theory describes its mechanical response.

While effective stress describes the transmission of forces within an already existing granular skeleton, the SEE framework describes the existence and stability of that skeleton itself. In this sense, the two approaches operate at different levels of description.

When the curvature of the effective energy landscape remains positive,

$$\frac{d^2 G_{\text{eff}}}{dn^2} > 0,$$

the system resides in a metastable phase in which a coherent granular skeleton exists. In this regime, classical soil mechanics applies and provides an accurate description of mechanical behaviour.

When the curvature vanishes,

$$\frac{d^2 G_{\text{eff}}}{dn^2} = 0,$$

the system reaches the spinodal boundary of the effective energy landscape. At this point, the metastable minimum disappears, and the granular skeleton loses its structural stability. In this regime, the assumptions underlying stress-based descriptions break down, because the load-bearing contact network itself no longer exists.

The SEE framework therefore provides a stability criterion at the level of the energy landscape, whereas effective stress theory describes the mechanical response within an already existing phase. The two approaches should thus be understood as fundamentally different but complementary descriptions of saturated granular systems.

In this sense, SEE can be interpreted as an energetic formulation of the conditions under which a load-bearing granular structure can exist, while classical soil mechanics describes the behaviour of that structure once it is established.

Section 9 – Discussion

The formulation developed in this work suggests that the stability of saturated granular packings can be understood in terms of an effective energy landscape governing the structural configuration of the grain network. In this picture, a load-bearing granular skeleton corresponds to a metastable minimum of the effective energy, while the disappearance of this minimum marks the loss of structural stability of the system.

This perspective places the SEE framework in close conceptual relation to energy-landscape approaches that have proven useful in many areas of physics dealing with disordered systems. In such approaches, the stability of a structure is determined by the curvature of an effective potential describing the configuration space of the system. Although granular materials are essentially athermal, the same conceptual framework can be applied, because the relevant energies arise from mechanical interactions and gravitational forces rather than from thermal fluctuations.

Within this interpretation, the SEE formulation can be viewed as a Landau-type description of a granular system, in which the porosity acts as a scalar order parameter and the effective energy landscape governs the existence of a mechanically stable phase. The metastable granular skeleton corresponds to a local minimum of this potential, while the loss of this minimum at vanishing curvature corresponds to a spinodal instability.

This interpretation provides a natural connection to the concept of jamming in granular physics. A jammed state corresponds to a mechanically stable configuration of the grain contact network capable of transmitting stresses. In the SEE framework, such a state is associated with a metastable minimum of the effective energy landscape. As the porosity increases and the

curvature of the potential decreases, the system approaches a marginally stable configuration in which the contact network becomes increasingly fragile.

The instability described by SEE can therefore be interpreted as a loss of a metastable granular phase, analogous to a spinodal transition in other physical systems. However, in saturated granular systems, this transition is not governed solely by packing geometry, but also by buoyancy. The stabilizing forces at grain contacts are controlled by the buoyancy-reduced grain weight

$$(\rho_s - \rho_f) \cdot g,$$

which sets the fundamental energy scale of the system. As a consequence, the stability of the granular network depends on both structural configuration and buoyancy-controlled gravity.

This interpretation provides a physically intuitive explanation for the abrupt collapse observed in loose saturated granular packings. As the system approaches the spinodal boundary, the effective stiffness of the granular skeleton vanishes, and the system becomes increasingly sensitive to perturbations. In this regime, even small disturbances can trigger large-scale structural rearrangements.

More generally, the SEE framework suggests that the stability of saturated granular systems is governed by the interplay between structural organization and buoyancy-controlled gravitational forcing. This perspective provides a unified energetic description of metastability, instability, and structural collapse in such systems.

At the same time, it is important to emphasize that the effective energy $G_{\text{eff}}(n)$ introduced in this work should be understood as a coarse-grained description rather than a thermodynamic potential derived from equilibrium statistical mechanics. The SEE framework does not rely on thermal fluctuations or entropy in the classical sense but instead captures the mechanical stability of the granular system through an effective energetic representation.

This distinction highlights the role of SEE as a bridge between classical geotechnical descriptions and modern physical approaches to disordered systems. By formulating the stability of saturated granular packings in terms of an effective energy landscape, the SEE framework provides a conceptual link between stress-based descriptions and energy-based approaches in granular physics.

Section 10 – Conclusions

In this work, a stability framework for saturated granular packings has been developed based on the concept of Static Enthalpy Equilibrium (SEE). The analysis shows that the existence of a load-bearing granular skeleton can be described in terms of an effective energy landscape governing the structural state of the system.

Within this formulation, the porosity n acts as a scalar order parameter that characterizes the configuration of the granular packing. The effective energy

$$G_{\text{eff}}(n) = G_{\text{str}}(n) + \frac{C}{1 - n}$$

captures the competition between structural resistance of the grain contact network and buoyancy-controlled gravitational forcing.

The stability of the granular skeleton is determined by the curvature of this energy landscape. Stable configurations correspond to metastable minima of the effective potential, while instability occurs when the curvature vanishes,

$$\frac{d^2 G_{\text{eff}}}{dn^2} = 0,$$

corresponding to a spinodal condition. At this point, the metastable minimum disappears and the granular skeleton loses its structural stability.

The dynamical analysis shows that the relaxation time of structural perturbations diverges as the curvature approaches zero,

$$\tau = \frac{1}{M \cdot \kappa},$$

providing a dynamic signature of the approaching instability. This behaviour corresponds to critical slowing down and reflects the progressive loss of stiffness of the granular network.

Within the Landau-type interpretation, the SEE framework can be understood as a coarse-grained description of a granular system in which the porosity acts as an order parameter and

the effective energy landscape governs the existence of a mechanically stable phase. The collapse of the granular skeleton can thus be interpreted as a spinodal loss of a metastable phase.

This perspective provides a direct connection between geotechnical observations of liquefaction and fundamental concepts of metastability and jamming in granular physics. It shows that the stability of saturated granular packings is controlled by the interplay between structural organization and buoyancy-controlled gravity.

At the same time, the SEE framework should be understood as an effective energetic description rather than a thermodynamic theory derived from equilibrium statistical mechanics. Its strength lies in providing a physically transparent stability criterion that complements classical stress-based approaches.

In this sense, SEE offers a unified framework for describing the existence and loss of mechanically stable granular structures and provides a basis for further theoretical and experimental investigations of instability phenomena in saturated granular systems.

Literaturverzeichnis

Iverson, R. (1997). *The physics of debris flows* (Bd. 35(3)). Review of Geophysics.

Liu, A., & Nagel, S. (1998). *Jamming is not just cool any more*. Nature.

Makse, H., & Kurchan, J. (2002). Testing thermodynamic approach to granular matter with numerical model of decisive experiment. *Nature*, 415, , S. 614-617.

O'Hern, C., Langer, S., Liu, A., & Nagel, S. (2003). Jamming at zero temperature and zero applied stress: The epitome of disorder. *Physical review E*, 68, 011306.

Seed, H., & Idriss, I. (1971). Simplified procedure for evaluation soil liquefaction potential. *J. of Soil Mech. and Found. Div., ASCE, Vol. 97, Nr. 9*, (<https://doi.org/10.1061/jsfeaq.0001662>).

van Hecke, M. (2010). Jamming of soft particles: geometry, mechanics, scaling and isostaticity. *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter*, 22, 033101.

Appendix A – Geometric Origin of the Gravitational Energy Term

In this appendix, the geometric origin of the gravitational contribution to the effective energy is derived.

Consider a granular column with cross-sectional area A containing a constant mass of grains. The solid grain volume is given by

$$V_s = (1 - n) \cdot V, \quad (\text{A } 1)$$

where n denotes the porosity and V the total volume of the system.

For a column geometry, the total volume can be written as

$$V = A \cdot H, \quad (\text{A } 2)$$

where H represents the height of the granular packing. Combining these relations yields

$$V_s = (1 - n) \cdot A \cdot H. \quad (\text{A } 3)$$

Since the mass of the grains remains constant during structural rearrangements, the solid volume V_s is fixed. The column height therefore varies with porosity according to

$$H = \frac{V_s}{A \cdot (1 - n)}. \quad (\text{A } 4)$$

As the packing becomes looser, the height of the granular column increases and the centre of mass of the grain assembly moves upward. The gravitational potential energy of the grains is proportional to the height of their centre of mass and to the buoyancy-reduced grain weight

$$(\rho_s - \rho_f) \cdot g.$$

Substituting the expression for the column height therefore yields

$$G_{\text{grav}}(n) \propto (\rho_s - \rho_f) g \frac{1}{1 - n}. \quad (\text{A } 5)$$

This result provides the geometric basis for the gravitational contribution used in the SEE formulation,

$$G_{\text{grav}}(n) = \frac{C}{1 - n}, \quad (\text{A } 6)$$

where C is proportional to the buoyancy-controlled gravitational energy scale.

Appendix B – Expansion of the Structural Energy

The structural energy $G_{\text{str}}(n)$ represents the mechanical resistance of the grain contact network to structural rearrangements. Its detailed functional form depends on the microscopic configuration of the packing, including contact geometry, friction, and packing structure.

For the stability analysis developed in this work, it is sufficient to assume that the structural energy is a smooth function of the porosity. Around a reference configuration n_0 , it can therefore be expanded as a Taylor series,

$$G_{\text{str}}(n) = G_{\text{str}}(n_0) + a_1(n - n_0) + \frac{a_2}{2}(n - n_0)^2 + \frac{a_3}{3}(n - n_0)^3 + \dots \quad (\text{B } 1)$$

This expansion corresponds to a Landau-type representation of the effective potential, in which the coefficients a_i encode the mechanical properties of the granular network.

Near a stationary configuration, the first derivative of the effective energy vanishes, and the stability of the system is governed by the second derivative,

$$\kappa = \frac{d^2 G_{\text{eff}}}{dn^2}. \quad (\text{B } 2)$$

Higher-order terms in the expansion determine the nonlinear behaviour of the system and are essential for capturing the loss of stability. In particular, a purely quadratic structural energy cannot produce a spinodal instability, since it does not allow for curvature softening at large porosities.

Appendix C – Linear Stability Analysis and Relaxation Time

The dynamical evolution of the structural state variable n is described by the relaxational equation

$$\dot{n} = -M \cdot \frac{dG_{\text{eff}}}{dn}, \quad (\text{C } 1)$$

where M is a mobility coefficient.

To analyse the dynamics near equilibrium, we consider small deviations from a stationary configuration n^* ,

$$n = n^* + \delta n. \quad (\text{C } 2)$$

Expanding the effective energy around this point yields

$$G_{\text{eff}}(n) \approx G^* + \frac{\kappa}{2} \cdot (\delta n)^2, \quad (\text{C } 3)$$

where

$$\kappa = \left. \frac{d^2 G_{\text{eff}}}{dn^2} \right|_{n^*}. \quad (\text{C } 4)$$

Substituting this approximation into the evolution equation gives

$$\delta \dot{n} = -M \cdot \kappa \cdot \delta n. \quad (\text{C } 5)$$

The solution corresponds to exponential relaxation,

$$\delta n(t) = \delta n(0) \cdot e^{-t/\tau}, \quad (\text{C } 6)$$

with characteristic relaxation time

$$\tau = \frac{1}{M \cdot \kappa}. \quad (\text{C } 7)$$

As the spinodal boundary is approached and $\kappa \rightarrow 0$, the relaxation time diverges, indicating critical slowing down.

Appendix D – Minimal Landau-Type Form and Stability Limit

The effective energy can be written as

$$G_{\text{eff}}(n) = G_{\text{str}}(n) + \frac{C}{1-n}. \quad (\text{D } 1)$$

To illustrate the mechanism of instability, consider a minimal nonlinear form of the structural energy,

$$G_{\text{str}}(n) = \frac{a}{2}(n - n_0)^2 - \frac{b}{3}(n - n_0)^3, \quad (\text{D } 2)$$

with $a > 0$ and $b > 0$.

The effective energy becomes

$$G_{\text{eff}}(n) = \frac{a}{2} \cdot (n - n_0)^2 - \frac{b}{3} \cdot (n - n_0)^3 + \frac{C}{1-n}. \quad (\text{D } 3)$$

The stability boundary is defined by

$$\frac{dG_{\text{eff}}}{dn} = 0, \quad \frac{d^2G_{\text{eff}}}{dn^2} = 0. \quad (\text{D } 4)$$

These conditions determine the critical porosity n^* at which the metastable minimum disappears. This minimal model illustrates that the instability arises from the competition between structural softening and gravitational destabilization.

Appendix E – Dimensionless Formulation

The stability problem can be expressed in dimensionless form by introducing a scaled energy,

$$\tilde{G}(n) = \tilde{G}_{\text{str}}(n) + \frac{\Lambda}{1-n}, \quad (\text{E } 1)$$

where Λ is a dimensionless parameter proportional to the buoyancy-controlled gravitational energy scale.

The curvature of the energy landscape becomes

$$\frac{d^2\tilde{G}}{dn^2} = \frac{d^2\tilde{G}_{\text{str}}}{dn^2} + \frac{2 \cdot \Lambda}{(1-n)^3}. \quad (\text{E } 2)$$

The spinodal boundary is therefore defined by

$$\frac{d^2 \widetilde{G}_{\text{str}}}{dn^2} + \frac{2 \cdot \Lambda}{(1-n)^3} = 0. \quad (\text{E } 3)$$

This formulation shows that the stability of the system is controlled by a competition between structural softening and gravitational forcing, with Λ acting as a control parameter.